

Diversity, biogeography, and chemically mediated interactions of toxigenic benthic marine dinoflagellates from Mexican coastal waters

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Abstract

Many benthic dinoflagellates produce polyketide-derived polyether toxins responsible for diverse seafood poisoning syndromes, such as diarrhetic shellfish poisoning and ciguatera fish poisoning. In Mexico, bHAB events have received recent public health and scientific attention, but many species lack molecular identification, and phylogeographic and toxigenic information remains limited. Our multidisciplinary project on bHAB taxa includes morphological and molecular characterization, phylogeography, and investigation of allelopathic and pharmacological bioactivity, supplemented with bacterial microbiome analysis. We first characterized the phylogeography and diversity of the genus *Prorocentrum* from Mexican coasts and investigated potential allelochemical effects of associated bacteria on growth and toxigenicity of members of the *Prorocentrum lima* species complex. Thus far, we have also completed the first phylogenetic study of benthic *Amphidinium* and registered two species (*A. theodorei* and *A. massartii*) for the first time from Mexico. Preliminary studies on the *in vitro* cytotoxic properties of *A. operculatum* and *Coolia malayensis* are also well advanced, demonstrating pharmacological potential through bioactivity against human cancer cell lines. The focus on functional diversity and species interactions yields valuable insights in evaluating toxin risk in the design and implementation of monitoring systems for bHABs and exploring biotechnological prospects for bioactive secondary metabolites from benthic species.

Keywords: *Amphidinium*, *Coolia*, *Prorocentrum*, phylogeny, *in vitro* cytotoxicity

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Introduction

Dinoflagellates are essential functional components of benthic food webs and are implicated in species interactions, especially with microeukaryotes and bacteria on epibenthic substrates and the surrounding microbiome (Boisnoir *et al.*, 2018; Richlen and Lobel, 2011). The dinoflagellate genus *Prorocentrum* Ehrenberg is widely distributed in coastal waters of Mexico and throughout Latin America (reviewed in Durán-Riveroll *et al.* (2019). Benthic representatives of *Prorocentrum* are known to produce diarrheagenic toxins, such as okadaic acid and certain dinophysistoxins, plus other polyketide-derived metabolites of uncertain toxicity or bioactivity (Hu *et al.*, 2010). The phylogeographical distribution, cell toxicity, toxin composition, and diversity of benthic *Prorocentrum lima* and *Prorocentrum hoffmannianum* species complexes, PLSC and PHSC, respectively, have been published (Cembella *et al.*, 2021). Nevertheless, such studies are limited to isolates from a few selected sites on the coasts of Mexico and do not represent the complete diversity of the genus at the infraspecific and population levels.

Members of the dinoflagellate genus *Amphidinium* Claparède *et* Lachmann are often abundant in benthic environments, including tropical and subtropical zones in Mexico, frequently attached to macrophytes. Some species have the capacity to synthesize bioactive polyketides, but the structures are poorly characterized in most cases, and studies are limited to a few species (Murray *et al.*, 2012). These polyketide metabolites of *Amphidinium* have shown biological activities worth further investigation as

potential pharmaceuticals or therapeutants (Mejía-Camacho *et al.*, 2021).

Species of the genus *Coolia* Meunier may produce cooliatoxin(s), polyketide analogs of yessotoxin (YTX), but the chemical structures of cooliatoxins have not been fully elucidated. Some members of the genus are known to produce bioactive metabolites in culture against several cancer cell lines (Boente-Juncal *et al.*, 2019) but the active components remain uncharacterized.

Some recent studies have evaluated the cytotoxic, antiproliferative, antibiotic, antifungal, and antidiabetic effects of benthic dinoflagellate metabolites as potential sources for novel drugs (Dewi *et al.*, 2018). The diversity and chemically mediated species interactions of benthic dinoflagellates in Mexican coastal waters are being studied from the morphological and molecular perspective for the species identification, phylogeography, chemical ecology, and production of bioactive metabolites with pharmacological potential. Herein we report preliminary highlights as representative of the emerging state of knowledge on diversity and species interactions.

Material and Methods

Isolation, culture, and harvest of Prorocentrum, Amphidinium, and Coolia species

Benthic dinoflagellate cells were isolated from macroalgae, seagrasses, and inanimate surfaces collected from Bahía de La Paz (Gulf of California), Veracruz (Gulf of Mexico), and Puerto Morelos (Caribbean

Sea). Experimental cultures of *Amphidinium* and *Coolia* were grown in GSe medium without soil extract, prepared from filtered autoclaved seawater at a salinity of 36. Cultures were initiated on a 12:12 h L:D cycle at 24 ± 1 °C with an illumination of $50 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ in 60 x 15 mm Petri plates for microscopic identification and DNA and ethanolic extraction. Subcultures of *Prorocentrum* spp. were transferred to Alfred Wegener Institute, Germany, and grown on K medium at 24 ± 1 °C on a 14:10 L:D cycle under illumination of $86 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. Exponentially growing *Prorocentrum* cultures (*ca.* 10^6 cells) were harvested by centrifugation (10 min, 3,000xg) for DNA sequencing (Cembella *et al.*, 2021) and for toxin analysis (Tarazona-Janampa *et al.* (2020) after esterase inactivation at 100 °C for 5 min.

DNA sequence analysis of Prorocentrum spp. Total DNA was extracted and processed with the Genomic DNA PowerSoil kit (Macherey-Nagel, Düren, Germany), following details in (Cembella *et al.*, 2021). The D1/D2 region of the 28S large subunit (LSU) rDNA and the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region (including ITS1, 5.8S subunit, and ITS2 sequences) were amplified from each total DNA extract by PCR. Sequencing products were analyzed on an ABI 3130 XL capillary sequencer (Applied Biosystems, Darmstadt, Germany) and the generated sequences were analyzed and assembled with CLC main workbench version 12.0.1.

Phylogenetic analysis included representative sequences of *P. lima sensu lato*, *P. lima*, *P. hoffmannianum*, and *P. belizeanum* from the Americas, Asia, and Europe, retrieved from GenBank2 (n = 68 for LSU and n = 72 for

ITS). Two data sets with 13 species were assembled, one for the LSU locus with 68 sequences, and another for the ITS locus with 72 sequences. Taxonomic sampling within *Prorocentrum* followed Chomérat *et al.* (2019), but with the addition of recently described species (Lim *et al.*, 2019; Luo *et al.*, 2017).

Toxin composition of Prorocentrum spp.

Analysis of DSP toxins, namely okadaic acid (OA) and dinophysistoxins (DTX), was performed as described in Tarazona-Janampa *et al.* (2020) by liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) following previous protocols (Krock *et al.*, 2008).

Molecular identification of Amphidinium spp. and Coolia spp.

Total DNA extraction of *Amphidinium* isolates AA38, AA60, AA105, and AA112, and *Coolia* isolates CA24, and CA55, was performed by a modified CTAB method according to Jørgensen *et al.* (2004). Approximately 1,450 base pairs (bp) of the D1 and D6 variable domains of LSU rDNA were amplified (Jørgensen *et al.*, 2004; Karafas *et al.*, 2017). PCR products were sequenced by seqXcel Inc. (California, U.S.A.). The NCBI database was accessed through BLASTn for species assignment.

Preparation of ethanolic extracts for cell assays

Amphidinium AA60 and *Coolia* CA24 cultures (13-50 mL) were harvested by centrifugation (35xg for 10 min). Seawater medium supernatants were removed and the pellets frozen at -65 °C. Biomass was extracted with 2 mL 100% ethanol. Complete cell disruption by repeated freeze-thaw cycles

was verified microscopically. The extracted material was centrifuged (6720×g) and the retained supernatant was filtered through a 0.2 μm syringe filter. The ethanolic extracts were lyophilized and later reconstituted for the *in vitro* assays.

Six human cancer cell lines were assayed for effects on growth after exposure to ethanolic extracts: U251 (human glioblastoma), PC-3 (human prostatic adenocarcinoma), K562 (human erythroleukemia), HCT-15 (human colorectal adenocarcinoma), MCF-7 (human mammary adenocarcinoma), and SKLU-1 (human lung adenocarcinoma). All cancer cell lines were obtained from the National Cancer Institute (NCI, Bethesda, MD, U.S.A.). The cell lines were cultured in RPMI-1640 medium supplemented and tested as described in Mejía-Camacho *et al.* (2021).

Results and Discussion

Diversity among Prorocentrum species complexes

Morphotaxonomic and phylogenetic analysis of ITS/5.8S rDNA sequences from *Prorocentrum* isolates from the Gulf of California, Gulf of Mexico and the Caribbean Sea defined five consistent clades with separation of the PLSC and PHSC, with details provided in Cembella *et al.* (2021). This study represents the largest (n = 67 isolates) chemodiversity analysis of polyketide-derived DSP toxins from any benthic dinoflagellate genus. Relative composition of certain analogs distinguished *P. lima* from *P. hoffmannianum sensu lato*, but without clear associations with substrate type or geographical origin within Mexican coastal waters. All *P. lima* and most (one exception) *P. hoffmannianum* isolates were toxicogenic, but

the total cell toxin content was not correlated among strains at the infraspecific level according to biogeographical distribution or origin.

Species identification and molecular diversity of Amphidinium

Cultured *Amphidinium* strains were assigned to species based on molecular criteria as follows: AA38, *A. theodorei*, AA60, *A. operculatum*, AA112, *A. massartii*, and AA105 *A. carterae*. To our knowledge, this is the first report of *A. theodorei* and *A. massartii* in Mexican coastal waters. *Amphidinium* species are notoriously difficult to identify based on morphological criteria alone because cells are fragile and variable in shape with few reliable surface details. The apparent absence of *A. theodorei* and *A. massartii* in records of benthic dinoflagellates from Mexico may be due to the previous lack of molecular studies of this genus in the region. Alignment of the LSU rDNA sequences of the D1-D6 region from *Amphidinium* placed all isolates from Mexican waters within the Operculatum clade, as currently defined, despite the high species diversity among sites (Figs. 1, 2).

Fig. 1. Phylogenetic tree (Bayesian inference) from LSU rDNA regions D1-D6.

Fig. 2. Phylogenetic tree (Bayesian inference) from LSU rDNA regions D1-D6.

In vitro cell activity of ethanolic extracts of *Coolia* and *Amphidinium*

The rRNA sequence analysis of *Coolia* CA24 and CA55 strains confirmed that these strains extracted belonged to *C. malayensis* and *C. monotis*, respectively. *In vitro* cell assays with ethanolic extracts of both *Coolia* strains against human cancer cell lines showed clear bioactive responses only with *C. malayensis* CA24 extracts.

Extracts of *C. malayensis* CA24 exhibited different inhibitory responses against various human cell lines when administered in fixed doses at 25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ (equivalent to 5,220 dinoflagellate cells mL^{-1}). The highest growth inhibition was apparent with MCF-7, HCT-15, and SKLU-1 cancer cell lines (Fig. 3).

Extracts of *A. operculatum* AA60 heavily inhibited the growth of MCF-7 and SKLU-1 cell lines (as for *C. malayensis* CA24)

when applied at 25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ (equivalent to 5,110 cells mL^{-1}). In contrast, however, all other cell lines were also inhibited to some extent ($> 13\%$) (Fig. 3). Ethanolic extracts of AA60 are generally more potent and with a broader activity spectrum than *Coolia* CA24 at comparable dosages.

Fig. 3. Growth inhibition of cell lines exposed to ethanolic extracts of *C. malayensis* CA24 and *A. operculatum* AA60 applied at 25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$.

This preliminary work has demonstrated diversity among benthic *Prorocentrum* from multiple sites on the Gulf of California, the Gulf of Mexico, and the Mexican Caribbean coasts. The next stage is to explore the role of the microbiome on growth and toxigenicity in an ecological context. For other genera such as *Coolia* and *Amphidinium*, the diversity range among species and populations from different regions must first be considered. The high chemodiversity in bioactive secondary metabolites, e.g., toxins and/or allelochemicals produced by the benthic dinoflagellates surveyed herein suggests that it is worthwhile to pursue further bioactivity screening. Biotechnological and pharmaceutical potential can only be critically evaluated by identification of the respective bioactive components and more

detailed screening over a wider range of concentrations. This will also assist in the implementation of rational risk assessment strategies for bHABs.

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